

APPENDIX 4 - WORKLOAD/EFFORT ASSESSMENT QUESTIONNAIRE

WORKLOAD/EFFORT ASSESSMENT QUESTIONNAIRE

Part 1 – Work Effort/Workload.

1) Rate the following on a scale of 0 to 100, related to the use of the Catalog.

A) Mental Demand:

How much mental and perceptual activity was required (e.g., thinking, deciding, calculating, remembering, looking, researching, etc.)? Was the task easy, simple, and straightforward (low end of the scale) or difficult, complex, and demanding?

Mental Demand	Low	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100	High
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B) Physical Demand

How much physical activity was required (e.g., pushing, pulling, turning, controlling, activating, etc.)? Was the task easy or demanding, slow or fast, calm or strenuous, restful or laborious?

Physical Demand	Low	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100	High
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C) Time Demand

How much time pressure did you feel due to the pace at which tasks or task elements occurred? Was the pace slow and sluggish (low end of the scale) or fast and frantic (high end of the scale)?

Time Demand	Low	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100	High
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D) Performance

How successful do you think you were in meeting the objectives of the task defined by the experimenter (or by yourself)? How satisfied were you with your performance in meeting these goals?

Performance	Excellent	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100	Bad
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E) Effort

How difficult was it for you to work (mentally and physically) to reach your current level of performance?

Effort	Low	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100	High
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F) Frustration

How insecure, discouraged, irritated, stressed, and bored versus confident, excited, content, relaxed, and calm did you feel during the task?

Frustration	Low	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100	High
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2) After evaluating the six dimensions of NASA TLX, select one dimension from each of the 15 comparisons, choosing the option that represents the most significant contribution to the workload of using CPRP.

A) Comparison 1:

- Mental Demand
- Physical Demand

B) Comparison 2:

- Time Demand
- Physical Demand

C) Comparison 3:

- Time Demand
- Frustration

D) Comparison 4:

- Time Demand
- Mental Demand

E) Comparison 5:

Performance

Physical Demand

F) Comparison 6:

Time Demand

Effort

G) Comparison 7:

Performance

Mental Demand

H) Comparison 8:

Frustration

Physical Demand

I) Comparison 9:

Performance

Frustration

J) Comparison 10:

Frustration

Mental Demand

K) Comparison 11:

Effort

Physical Demand

L) Comparison 12:

Performance

Effort

M) Comparison 13:

Effort

Mental Demand

N) Comparison 14:

Time Demand

Performance

O) Comparison 15:

Effort

Frustration